

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

REFLECTION OF SOCIAL AND POLITICAL LIFE OF NORTHERN AZERBAIJAN IN THE END OF XIX AND BEGINNING OF XX CENTURY IN SOURCES AND HISTORIOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

The reactionary policy of the ruling circles of the Russian Empire, the development of capitalist relations after the bourgeois reforms gave impetus to the formation of the Azerbaijani nation and the beginning of the national movement in Northern Azerbaijan, at the end of the XIX century. At the end of the XIX century - the beginning of the XX century, the period of the rise of national thinking in Northern Azerbaijan is the period when a number of public organizations, charitable societies, press agencies and the development of art and dramaturgy were established.

The period of the XIX-early XX centuries was a turbulent but proud period of Azerbaijani historiography, which was the focus of researchers' attention, and valuable scientific works were created.

Keywords: socio-political situation, public organizations, national press, national thinking, Azerbaijani historiography.

Beginning with the second half of the XIX century, progress was observed in the public thinking of the people in Northern Azerbaijan, the spread of enlightenment, and drama and art became widespread. It was at this time that the first schools for education and science were opened in cities and villages, newspapers and journals, and books were published. Although the intellectual representatives of Azerbaijan were persecuted and insulted by the reactionary forces, they mobilized all their forces in the way of educating the people. The first Russian-Tatar (Azerbaijani) school was opened in Baku as a result of the efforts of intellectuals. This was the period of the awakening of national-democratic thinking in the history of the Azerbaijani people. Following the change in the public worldview, tsarist Russia did not miss the strict control of the democratic-minded national press, and tried to limit the rights and opportunities of the masses. Many leading representatives of national-democratic ideas - educators, teachers, especially press workers - were persecuted, punished and fined. The struggle of prominent intellectuals and public figures of the time, Mirza Fatali Akhundov, Hasan Bey Zardabi, and other well-known figures for public education revealed the need to change the eastern education system and create modern educational schools. As a result of H. Zardabi's initiative and principled action, in 1871, the foundation of the first national-public society in the field of education in Azerbaijan - "Society to help Muslim children who are studying" was established. "Akinçi", which gives a strong impetus to the development of national thinking, and has a power that cannot be compared with any other means in this sense, began to be published.

In the study of the important stage of the history of Azerbaijan at the end of the XIX century and the beginning of the XX century, which was accompanied by serious economic, social and political changes sources of the period, archives of press bodies, as well as scientific works published in different years are of great importance.

The collection of laws of the Russian Empire prepared at the beginning of the Nicholas period under the leadership of M.Speransky and republished several times until the October Revolution, is an important source in creating a broad image of the social and political life of Northern Azerbaijan, which was a part of the empire in the XIX and early XX centuries. In that source, social relations, public education under state control, administration in governorates and districts, judicial system and many other important issues were reflected. [15]. Although pre-revolutionary researchers wrote about many loopholes in civil legislation in the collection (rights and obligations in family relations, police and financial violations), in general the corpus provides valuable facts about the period.

Tsarist Senator A.M. Kuzminski's reports on Baku and Baku Governorate occupy a special place in the collection of social and political information from the beginning of the 20th century [16]. The reports provide information about the national bourgeoisie of Azerbaijan and its activities in public life. A number of interesting facts on the subject were included in the collection [18] of documents on the policy of tsarism in the South Caucasus.

In the learning of the topic, the documents of the State Historical Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the archival materials of the newspapers "Kapsiy", "Baku", "Taraqi", "Iqbal", "Nijat", "Irshad", "Basirat", "Açığ Soz" which played a special role in the development of the Azerbaijani press at the end of the XIX century and the beginning of the XX century are also irreplaceable. Although the communist ideology, which ruled for many years, did not allow us to reflect the social and political life in North Azerbaijan in the late XIX and early XX centuries, a large number of rich social and political events were covered in the press. For this reason, taking advantage of the opportunities provided by independence, the objective study of press organizations remains an important task for scientists.

It is clear from the documents of the State Historical Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan that at the end of the XIX and the beginning of the XX centuries, public organizations played an important role in the formation of national thinking in Azerbaijan, and the opening of branches of such organizations was supported by the masses of the people. For example, in January 1907, amendments were made to the Charter in order to satisfy the request of the residents of Shamakhi to open a branch of the "Nashri maarif" organization in Shamakhi. The project was prepared by Ahmed Bey Agayev, a member of the management board of the organization, and submitted to the state authorities in order to obtain permission [2]. In the documents of the State Historical Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan, there are numerous facts about the national awakening of the people and the opening of centers of enlightenment at the request of the people in Shamakhi, Goychay, Guba, Ganja, Astara, Neftchala, Zagatala, Agdash, Shusha, Devechi and other regions.

Some information related to the research topic was collected in the Archive of the National Library of Azerbaijan. Among them, the existing materials about the charter, founders and activities of the "Baku Muslim Unas Society-Charity" adopted in 1914 contain valuable information about the social and political life of Azerbaijan. It is clear from the archival documents that the funds of the organization were mainly collected from membership fees, funds received from official offices, interest of bank investments owned by the organization, properties of the organization and other such sources of income [6].

Until 1896, the charters of public organizations such as education, science, enlightenment, and charity operating in the Russian Empire were based on uniform legislative rules in accordance with the requirements of the time. The charters of organizations registered with the state on the basis of official permits by local governing bodies - the governor-general or the mayor are sources of information about the social and political problems of the Azerbaijani organization and government-people-philanthropy relations. In the Charter of the "Baku Muslim Charitable Organization", the establishment of a special press body was not only aimed at educating and informing the population. One of the main goals here was charity. Thus, during the years of the First World War, the organization that supplied food and other necessary products to the Turkish-Muslim population who became refugees in the war and suffered losses, needed the financial resources obtained from the sale of the newspaper. In the spring of 1917, Muslim and non-Muslim refugees from Turkey and the Caucasian front were also able to benefit from the charitable activities of the organization [7].

As is known, the national press has played an important role in the history, culture, and social-political thinking of the people, including the people of Azerbaijan. For the first time in the Middle East, the national press in North Azerbaijan tried to make its contribution to the evolution of public organizations, and devoted space on the pages of the newspaper to issues that would ensure development in the field of education, science, culture, as well as in the everyday life of the

people. When the press of the time talked about the socio-political events taking place in the society, it contrasted the attitude of the national bourgeoisie and the intellectuals, and conveyed to the readers the support of the national bourgeoisie for the existing regime - tsarism, and the desire of the intellectuals to replace the monarchy with democracy in a unique way. In 1907, M.A. Rasulzade's article published in "Takamul" newspaper was about "five freedoms", where the author's press was called "second freedom" [11].

At the beginning of the XX century, the press agencies of Azerbaijan played the important role in the study of social activity and in conveying the political landscape to future generations. In the materials of the newspapers related to "Baku Muslim Charitable Society", the participation of members of the organization's board of directors, government representatives and intellectuals in the groundbreaking ceremony of the historical "Ismailiyya" building was covered in detail. According to the information, the "Ismailiyya" building was supposed to consist of three floors. On the first floor - a commercial sales center (shop) for the income of the organization, on the second floor - a school for poor and deprived Muslim children, on the third floor a library-reading room, where the population could use books, newspapers and magazines free of charge [12].

A certain part of the information related to the study of the social and political life of the period is stored in the archives of the "Baku" newspaper. It is clear from the 1906 issue of the "Baku" newspaper that at the beginning of the XX century, the "Nicat" Baku Muslim educational organization, operating on the basis of the Charter approved by the state authorities, had important activity in the national-cultural development of the people and the formation of educational ideas. The "Irshad" newspaper is full of valuable information about the powerful staff potential of "Nijat" Baku Muslim educational organization, which unites big entrepreneurs and intellectuals.

The development of capitalist relations led to the selection of Baku, as a major economic, financial and cultural center in the South Caucasus region at the beginning of the XX century. Large banks were opened in the city, the Baku-Tbilisi railway began to operate, Caspian shipping developed. Against the background of new social relations, tsarism had to make compromises, therefore the "Manifesto" signed by the government recognized ordinary human rights such as personal integrity, freedom of speech, freedom of conscience, and allowed events and gatherings.

"Taraqqi" newspaper published articles about the great importance of "Nicat" society to national moral values, the development of Azerbaijani language and literature, and wrote information about the internal rules of the organization, which are not reflected in the Charter. The most important of the internal rules was that the meetings of the board of directors should be conducted in the Azerbaijani language, and regardless of the identity of the participants, they should speak only in the Azerbaijani language. From the materials of the "Baku News" press, it is known that "Saadat", which operated in the early XX century, fought against religious superstition in its organizational activities,

and rendered special services in the spread of true, healthy religious literacy. Referring to the 1907 issues of the press, it is known that the program project was developed by the organization's management board for the purpose of real religious education, and this project was reflected in the Charter. According to that program, the organization plans to open a public reading room, a library, as well as publish books for children studying in schools and madrasas, publish its news in the Azerbaijani language, open a library for free distribution and free sale of books, create pedagogical courses, hold a teachers' congress, and organize spiritual it meant sending worthy students who had graduated from school to foreign countries to continue their education, organizing evening courses, scientific talks and literary evenings, opening boarding houses near schools and madrasas [14; 20; 3; 4]. The campaign of financial assistance to the "Saadat" organization, which plans to implement important projects, and the active participation of Baku millionaires in this campaign were reflected in the materials of the "Yeni Iqbal" newspaper.

In the second half of the XIX century - the beginning of the XX century, the socio-political situation in Azerbaijan was investigated both in the Soviet historiography and in the modern historiography of the homeland, the national awakening, the enlightenment movement, the development of school education were studied, and the attitude to the literary environment of the time and the activities of social and political parties was reported in the scientific literature. The socio-political landscape of Azerbaijan at this time found its place in the works of Muhammad Amin Rasulzadeh, Hasan Bey Agayev, Dadash Bunyadzadeh, Huseyn Naseh Alizadeh, Haji Ibrahim Gasimov, Hanifa Khanum Malikova and other intellectuals.

In the period after the independence of Azerbaijan, the study of the history of the early XIX and XX centuries became prominent. S. Aliyarli, D. Seyidzade, D. Huseynova, I. Baghirova, I. Musayev, M. Ismayilov, S. Talibova and other historians have become the object of research. One of the researchers who first paid attention to the topic, S. Aliyarli, in his article entitled "The first stages of the national movement", refused to count the beginning of the national movement in Azerbaijan from 1905, and called the years 1875-1905 the first stage of political ideological foundations - the "Akinchi stage".

In the monograph "Social and political movement in Azerbaijan (end of the XIX century - beginning of the XX century)" published in Baku at the end of the last century, researcher S. Suleymanova conducted valuable research directly related to the topic and obtained important results. Thus, when S. Suleymanova spoke about the reasons for the creation of the "Muslim charity organization", she connected it not only with helping the poor, but also with the purpose of caring for those who suffered from inter-ethnic conflicts (in 1905-1906) and brought interesting archival documents into scientific circulation [10].

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Among the researchers of the 1990s who paid attention to the topic, we can name the prominent historian M. Ismayilov. Valuable scientific facts about social and political movement in Azerbaijan are reflected in M. Ismayilov's work dedicated to the philanthropic activities of the representative of the national bourgeoisie of Azerbaijan H.Z. Taghiyev at the beginning of the XX century. [8] M. Ismayilov, who chose the activities of patron Z. Taghiyev in the socio-political life of Baku as an object of research, showed the traces of a prominent personality in various fields of the national economy, and highly appreciated his activities in the Baku Duma as a political figure.

Historian-scientist D.S. Huseynova's research work dedicated to the activity of Azerbaijani intellectuals in the late XIX and early XX centuries highlights the service of intellectuals in the formation of national-social consciousness. [17] The author evaluates the role of graduates of Russian universities, as well as French, German, and English universities in the formation of Azerbaijani intellectuals, and confirms that those intellectuals are the leading force in the social and political life of the country. D. Huseynova sees Azerbaijani intellectuals as products of European and traditional Islamic civilizations and calls them catalysts of fundamental changes in Azerbaijani society.

The researches of D. Seyidzadeh in the historiography of the homeland also made important contributions to the study of the investigated problem. In the research work of D. Seyidzade, the struggle of the national bourgeoisie of Azerbaijan, prominent ideologues of Azerbaijan in terms of the development of science, education and national culture was extensively discussed at the beginning of the XX century. The research work is important in terms of examining the initial conditions of the activity of national-public organizations [9]. The researcher, who focuses on the political direction of the subject, in his other work talks about the unity of representatives of the national bourgeoisie against riots, the creation of a committee under the name of maintaining order, highlights the measures against the labor protests of 1905, as well as the activities of the Baku City Duma [19].

Historian-scientist I. Baghirova's monograph dedicated to the activities of Azerbaijan's political parties and organizations is also important in terms of the investigation of socio-political processes and the characterization of the political environment in which national-social organizations operate in the studied period [13]. At the beginning of the last century, the author conducted serious research in the direction of reflecting the full picture of the political life of Azerbaijan, and turned important issues such as the formation of existing parties, their activities, and their relationship to the

existing regime into the object of research. In the monograph, not only Muslim, but also Christian (including Russian, Armenian) parties, Zionist and anarchist organizations were analyzed, and the impact of the collapse of the monarchy in Russia on the socio-political life of Azerbaijan was studied.

One of the valuable works related to the investigation of the problem is A. Bayramoglu's study entitled "Education and Enlightenment in Shamakhi (literary environment from the middle of the 19th century to March 1918)" published in 1997 [5]. The book examines the emergence and development of education and culture, including the literary movement of enlightenment in Azerbaijan from the middle of the 19th century to the March massacres of 1918, on the example of Shamakhi, which has an ancient history and rich literary traditions, and gives a scientific assessment of socio-political events. With reference to scientific-historical sources, archival materials and literary-artistic examples, the author illuminates the landscape of our social-literary and national cultural thought history for the first time in a regional aspect.

One of the attention-grabbing works related to this important period of Azerbaijani historiography belongs to J. Allahverdiyev. The author's "Iravan Literary Environment" published in 2010 helped to illuminate one or another aspect of the investigated problem. In his work, the author talks extensively about the activities of prominent Azerbaijani intellectuals who played a major role in the formation and development of Azerbaijan's literary environment in Yerevan and demonstrated national will, the problems faced by Azerbaijani Turks in the context of Armenian chauvinism, the role of the native language press, and educational and educational issues [1].

The reactionary policy of the tsarist ruling circles and the development of capitalist relations after the bourgeois reforms gave impetus to the formation of the Azerbaijani nation and the beginning of the national movement in Northern Azerbaijan at the end of the XIX century. At present, the in-depth study of the socio-political landscape of this period based on the new national theory is one of the important issues of Azerbaijan's history. The relevance of the problem should not be measured only by looking at the topic from new positions, by conducting a critical analysis. This is also important from the point of view of laying the foundations of the initial conditions for the creation of the

democratic model of the national state in Azerbaijan at the beginning of the XX century.

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